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Grasping at the Tendrils of a Slipping Dream: The Connotations of Ephemerality in Anaïs Nin's *A Spy in the House of Love*

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Abstract:

Developing upon José Esteban Muñoz's theorisation of the "ephemera", this paper seeks to repurpose the same, in order to identify an adoption of the ephemerality principle in Anaïs Nin's *A Spy in the House of Love*. Identifying three branches of this principle, namely textual ephemerality, material ephemerality and ephemerality of identity, this paper undertakes a close study of the novella to deepen literary understanding of Nin's conscious adoption of a gendered aesthetics. Furthermore, it seeks to understand how Nin, through the adoption of the ephemerality principle, tries to give voice to suppressed female sexuality, something that she felt could not be holistically explored through a male model of writing. It is only by consciously eluding any and all attempts at delineation that Nin provides clues to unravel the character of Sabina, and therefore, her stylistic rebellion that sought to embody female subjectivity through literary ambiguity.

Keywords: Anaïs Nin, Ephemerality, Female Sexuality, Gendered Stylistics.

Upon finishing Anaïs Nin's *A Spy in the House of Love*, the first and foremost thing that might strike the reader is the element of ephemerality suffused in every nook and cranny within the text. The novel, or rather, the novella exhibits an exquisitely queer dreamlike quality

to it— it makes one believe that they are inhabiting a state that is located almost on the fringes of one's consciousness and influences one to grasp at the tendrils of the effervescent dream. The novella is slippery and eludes any attempt at delineation. Clearly, that assumes the central binding principle of the novella. It refuses to be classified, characterised, and defined, much like its central character, Sabina. Anaïs Nin fashions a protagonist who resists any attempt at signification, and unassumingly seems to revel in her refusal to be pinned down— both by her lovers, and the readers. Now, what is this “ephemeral” that seems to be the topic in focus? Can it be used as a critical tool of analysis to arrive at a deeper understanding of Sabina, and in extension, Anaïs Nin? To go down a tangential route, José Esteban Muñoz in “Ephemera as Evidence: Introductory Notes to Queer Acts”, describes “ephemera” as a “modality of anti-rigor” that “reformulates and expands our understanding of materiality”. He consciously links it to “alternate modes of textuality and narrativity” that do not “...rest on epistemological foundations but is instead interested in following traces, glimmers, residues, and specks of things” (Muñoz, 10). While Muñoz in this particular essay, is interested in the ephemera as the principle of indeterminacy that is profoundly queer in its refashioning of lived materiality, this paper argues that Nin too, in this novel, seeks to refashion literary reality through an adoption of the ephemerality principle— a conscious mystification at work in the novel that leaves both Sabina's lovers and the readers wanting more. This paper seeks to embody Sylvia Wynters' call to decipher, rather than interpret, as quoted by Muñoz in the same essay:

Rather than seeking to "rhetorically demystify," a deciphering turn seeks to decipher what a process of rhetorical mystification does. It seeks to identify not what texts and their signifying practices can be interpreted to mean but what they can be deciphered to do, it also seeks to evaluate the "illocutionary force" and procedures with which they do what they do. (Wynters quoted in Muñoz, 12)

However, the question arises, was Nin's adoption of this ephemerality principle a conscious one? To answer that, one has to take a detour to Nin's notorious collection of erotic short stories published posthumously in 1977, *Delta of Venus*. In the Preface to this collection, a selection of her diary entries, starting from April, 1940 has been provided to offer, perhaps, a contextual clarification for the erotic short stories that are to follow in this anthology. As can be ascertained from the same, in April 1940, a certain book collector offered Henry Miller the deal of writing erotic stories for hundred dollars a month. Soon, in the following December, Miller introduced Nin to this collector to take over his role. As Nin started writing, the only consistent feedback she got was to cut out all poetry and only focus on sex. Every time she got a call from this anonymous patron, the old man only asked for one thing- cold, dry, clinical sex deprived of any touch of warmth that might erupt from a kindling of love, a literary record of sex only as a mechanical act, of a calculated interaction by instinct, and animalistic in its realisation. Writing for this strange patron, Nin recorded in her diary entry from February 1941, "I had a feeling that Pandora's box contained the mysteries of woman's sensuality, so different from man's and for which man's language was inadequate" (16). Taking up this issue of supposed difference between the masculine treatment of sex and its feminine counterpart, Nin elaborates in the postscript to this Preface that this task of writing erotica for the old man, drove to her the realisation of how much the masculine model of writing was inadequate to capture female sensuality— a supposed mystery that lets itself be unravelled only by revelling in its ambiguity. Female sexuality, as can be ascertained to be Nin's opinion in this postscript, can never be fully explored if one were to erase the emotional capacity inherent in the sexual act. She writes:

Women, I thought, were more apt to fuse sex with emotion, with love, and to single out one man rather than be promiscuous. This became apparent to me as I wrote the novels and the *Diary*, and I saw it even more clearly when I began to teach. But although

women's attitude towards sex was quite distinct from that of men, we had not yet learned to write about it. (Nin, 20)

If female sexuality can be encountered only through the ambiguous and the emotional, what better way to uphold that belief than a literary record that is created through a conscious adoption of the ephemerality principle? If the ephemera, as defined by Muñoz, is the one more interested in recording the traces than the absolute, it is but logical to attribute Nin upholding the same in *A Spy in the House of Love* in order to give voice to female sexuality. As will be further explored in this paper, her treatment of the novella never depicts but only indicates. It is a tale constantly blurring unto itself, always teetering on the edge of an aphrodisiac diffusion. It is this embedded sense of ephemeral effervescence that makes the novella stand out on its own and carve out a decided niche for itself. *A Spy in the House of Love* makes the reader feel like they are spying themselves- peeking through a keyhole at the extremely private wanderings of Sabina. However, the keyhole, and consequently Sabina herself, seems prone to vanishing into thin air at any moment. Her convoluted wanderings and her many disguises keep one on their tiptoes, perennially guessing at who the real Sabina is. What arises, therefore, are different variations of the ephemerality principle in the crafting of the novella. For the sake of brevity, this paper identifies mainly three branches of this ephemerality principle in the text, namely, textual ephemerality, material ephemerality and ephemerality of identity. Through an exploration of these three branches, this paper shall undertake a closer inspection of Nin's motive to write on and embody female sexuality in the fashioning of this novella, one that is born out of an urgent urge to give voice to female subjectivity in literature.

Textual Ephemerality:

In its refusal to represent the dogged reality, there is a highly refreshing quality of freedom to the novella. Anaïs Nin writes in her *The Novel of the Future*, "...that one could only

find reality by discarding realism” (Nin, 12). She further elaborates that this reality in question refers to “psychological reality” (Nin, *ibid*). To truthfully construct the inner workings of the mind, one must discard and give up one’s commitment to social reality. In order to capture the elaborate and intricate system of the unconscious, one must vehemently sacrifice the familiarity of the conscious. It is perhaps because of this reason that the narrative quality of *A Spy in the House of Love* is infused with a certain dream-like quality. To fall back upon *The Novel of the Future* where she writes:

As a prose poet becoming fascinated with a rich source of images, I concentrated on describing the dream world, perhaps tempted by the difficulties involved. Obviously, the physical world is easier to describe. The first misunderstanding about my work which arose and has continued to the present was that I was writing dreamlike and unreal stories. (Nin, 18)

In the novella, the narrative structure never assumes a concrete quality to itself. Rather, it accentuates the mystery of the plot and pushes the reader into occupying a trance-like realm. None of the settings seems solid enough. Whether it is a bar or a hotel or a mere road, Nin makes us believe that all of them might just be manifestations of Sabina’s guilty conscience. They could very well be make-believe. No description is meted out to the reader if they do not serve a symbolic purpose. When Sabina encounters the row of trucks on 18th St, she is intimidated by their looming presence over her. She feels dwarfed in front of their menacing stature, almost feeling as if they would extinguish her.

Sabina felt a shrinking of her whole body, and as she shrank from the noise, the trucks seem to enlarge in her eyes, their scale becoming enormous world of menacing giants. She felt her bones fragile in her sandals. She felt brittle and crushable. (Nin, 11)

In this short excerpt, it is quite evident that the looming trucks assume an almost symbolic power to overwhelm Sabina, a source of intimidation that at first might seem quite incongruous, keeping in mind that she is a thirty-year-old woman. However, consequently, it appears to be quite plausible given that the character of Sabina is seen to be plagued by an incessant guilty conscience that almost always seems to be on the brink of engulfing her entire persona. Nin does elaborate on this conscious choice to eliminate and subtract details in *The Novel of the Future*. As she says, as a writer, she is not at all interested in outward markers of a character's persona such as their nationality, age or background. She deems this "passport identification" quite unnecessary and superficial in the process of creating a fictive character. She writes:

I became very conscious of character as geological strata. Levels. I began very early to say I would only include the furniture if it was part of the symbolic drama, that is if it was significant, if it too played a role in the revelation of character. I did the same with costume. (Nin, 76)

One could perhaps apply the same principle in trying to decode Sabina's cape. The act of donning the cape transforms into an act of self-preservation for Sabina. It provides her with the necessary boost to her confidence and adds a bit of "swagger" to her step. In Sabina's imagination, the cape transforms into a magical armour, one that provides her with the necessary protection required for her everyday battles. At the same time, "...the cape held within its fold something of what she imagined was a quality possessed exclusively by man: some dash, some audacity, some swagger of freedom denied to woman" (Nin, 10). This mode of selective description allows Nin to augment the fictive world inhabited by Sabina with a certain marvellous effervescence. The descriptions provided do not serve the purpose of grounding the novella in reality. Rather, it only serves the intention of unmooring the reader, of enhancing the dreamlike evanescent quality of the narrative. One is reminded of André

Breton's admission of his distaste for the descriptions of the mundane in realist novels in his *Manifesto of Surrealism*. He confesses, "I do not take particular note of the empty moments of my life, that it may be unworthy for any man to crystallize those which seem to him to be so. I shall with your permission, *ignore* the description of that room, and many more" (Breton, 8). Maybe this is what Nin is trying to avoid. By not providing concrete descriptions of the setting, she seeks to invest in her novella a certain kind of fluid temporality- thereby establishing the fluidity in the character of Sabina herself.

Material Ephemerality:

The body in the text assumes an element of liminality. Just as Sabina deludes signification, so too does the body. The act of desiring itself becomes a fundamentally ephemeral act, destined to evaporate at the end right from the very beginning. The desiring body attaches to itself a mythical centrality to its very construction. Therein lies its beauty. The female desiring body is absolute in its centrality to the text. Just as a myth can have different versions abound, so too does the female body in the novella. However, unlike varying versions of a myth, the female body is constrained to the impermanence of existence. Irigaray writes, "Woman's desire would not be expected to speak the same language as man's; woman's desire has doubtless been submerged by the logic that has dominated the West since the time of the Greeks" (25). Thus, the desiring act becomes a pure abstraction. It never materialises into permanence. The waltz of desire can never be sure-footed. Bound by temporality, the pleasure sought after is concentrated into one tiny moment before it dissipates into nothingness. Just as the body yearns for "la petit mort" or the little death, so too does Sabina in creating these multiple avenues of pleasure. The desire that is marked by its death is what draws Sabina into her structures of multiplicities. In this act of active desiring, she contains in herself all women and no woman. She is unique yet multiple. To fall back upon Irigaray, "Her sexuality is always

at least double, goes even further: it is plural” (Irigaray, 28). One can never fully define her. Moreover, in this construction of plurality is embedded a strong sense of capricious incomprehensibility. Following the tacit agreement between Philip and Sabina to indulge in a sexual liaison, she identifies in his gaze how she is not anymore “the unique Sabina” cherished by her husband Alan, but just a woman with whom he is going to engage in sexual pleasure. “It was the alchemy of desire fixing itself upon the incarnation of all women into Sabina for a moment but as easily by a second processable to alchemize Sabina into many others” (Nin, 27). This feverish desire to consume and possess all women, however, never comes to be fully materialized for Philip. Sabina offers him only a version of herself and never the real her, the whole her. She fragments herself into different versions for her different lovers to grasp at the transitory tendrils of her pleasure. Her sexual trysts with her lovers transcend into an exploration of her own “autoeroticism” (Irigaray, 26). Nevertheless, just like fire inevitably turns into ash, so too does desire. The heady realization of desire in the final act almost always gives way to a hangover of the senses, of which the primary architect is guilt. Nin writes, “...this sensation was no different than drunkenness, and that it would vanish like ecstasies of drink, leaving her the next day even more shaky, even weaker at the core, deflated defeated, possessing nothing within herself” (29). The act of desiring thus assumes a permanent ephemerality in the psyche of Sabina, short-lived but brilliant, leaving in its wake the debris of her soul.

Sex in the text is never defined but always implied. This can be most clearly beheld in this short excerpt from the novella:

Desire made a volcanic island, on which they lay in a trance, feeling the subterranean whirls lying beneath them, dance floor and table and the magnetic blues uprooted by desire, the avalanches of the body's tremors. Beneath the delicate skin, the tendrils of secret hair, the indentations and valleys of flesh, the volcanic lava flowed, desire

incandescent, and where it burned the voices of the blues being sung became a harsh wilderness cry, bird and animal's untamed cry of pleasure and cry of danger and cry of fear and cry of childbirth and cry of wound pain from the same hoarse delta of nature's pits. (Nin, 32)

What is perhaps most fascinating about the novella is this intoxicating experimentation with the carnal. In the deft fingers of Nin, sex loses its base earthiness and assumes a piquant aestheticisation of the senses. It transforms into an abstract art from which all signifiers of identification have been removed. Sex becomes an enigma- a puzzle that does not need to be solved, a crypt that does not ask to be explored. Nin's reference to Marcel Duchamp's 1912 painting, "A Nude Descending a Staircase", assumes a prominent significance in such a scenario. Just as Duchamp's painting strips the body of its carnal aspect— only focussing on the nude body in motion— so too does Nin, while focussing on sex. There is a fluidity that is ingrained into the sexual act- a fluidity of motion that cannot be seized and arrested into a singular moment. Sex in the novella blurs into itself. Yet, it never loses its delicacy, its softness. Even in its abstraction, sex never loses its grace. It transforms into Sabina's "moon-baths"- dangerously ephemeral with the potency to extend the moment of eroticism into an infinity. Sex for Sabina becomes a "courtesan depositor of multiple desires" (Nin, 37). Thus, female sexuality in the novella assumes a polymorphous incoherence whose meaning remains in a constant state of deferment. Never allowing itself to be signified, it can only be experienced and grasped as fragments, both by Sabina and her lovers, as well as the readers.

While the elements of sex and desire intensify quite strongly the principle of material ephemerality, what augments it further is the importance of liminal locations in the novel. These sites of transience, ones which are not grounded in any kind of specificities, are the ones dearest to Sabina. They constitute her own safe havens, away from any kind of perception.

These locales, such as the cabs or the buses or even bathrooms, steeped in their material liminality, are the true witnesses to the unmasked Sabina. These locales emphasise for Sabina the fact that she is just passing through- she is not meant to stay anywhere. While all her lovers only get access to a version of Sabina that has been curated to suit their specific needs, in these liminal spaces, Sabina can just exist for herself and let go. For her, these liminal spaces represent “the moment of non-living, non-desiring” (Nin, 45). They are her “neutral zone of safety” (Nin, 43). In their liminality, these spaces become infinite for her. The sense of ephemerality that is ingrained into Sabina, spills over into her desire to inhabit locales that not constrained by the quotidian. She searches for the marvellous in her lovers' bedrooms, hoping against hope to get a chance to dwell in the infinite.

She realized that it was this illimitable space she had expected to find in every lover's room, the sea, the mountains visible all around, the world shut off on one side. A hearth without a roof or walls, growing between trees, a floor through which wild flowers pushed to show smiling faces, a column housing stray birds, temples and pyramids and baroque churches in the distance. (Nin, 57)

However, quite ironically yet inadvertently, she has to depart from these locations, simply because they exist to be taken leave of. At one point or another, much to her disappointment, Sabina has to cross the threshold of her safe zones into her fragmented reality.

Ephemerality of Identity:

Despite everything, the principle of ephemerality might shine through the brightest through the element of ephemerality of identity. Sabina's masquerading tendencies become the cornerstone of plot progression in the novella. She disguises herself as different personas in front of different individuals- to be interpreted differently according to their needs and sensibilities. “The faces and the figures of her personages appeared half drawn; and when the

lie detector had just begun to perceive them, another face and figure were interposed as in a dream” (Nin, 7). Sabina seems perennially out of reach, constantly a moment away from vanishing into thin air. When Alan says, “I want my own Sabina back” (Nin, 17), one wonders which version of Sabina is his Sabina. For Philip, she casts herself into the role of Don Juana, for Alan, the diffident, docile wife in need of protection, for Mambo, the stubborn receptacle of his angry desire, for John, a confidante for his war-born traumas, and for Donald, a replacement for his mother. She dons and sheds these roles with an effortless ease that marks the calibre of a true actress. In his letter to Sabina, Donald writes, “Acting in you is a revelation” (Nin, 89). No other words could be truer when it comes to Sabina. She personifies the very ephemerality that suffuses the entire novella. Yet, this ephemerality also comes with a curse. In the wake of fragmenting herself to suit the needs of her different lovers, she has to come face-to-face with her divided self. Irigaray writes:

Must this multiplicity of female desire and female language be understood as shards, scattered remnants of a violated sexuality? A sexuality denied? The question has no simple answer. The rejection, the exclusion of a female imaginary certainly puts woman in the position of experiencing herself only fragmentarily, in the little-structured margins of a dominant ideology, as waste, or excess, what is left of a mirror invested by the (masculine) "subject" to reflect himself, to copy himself. Moreover, the role of "femininity" is prescribed by this masculine specula(riza)tion and corresponds scarcely at all to woman's desire, which may be recovered only in secret, in hiding, with anxiety and guilt. (30)

Unable to reveal herself fully to anyone, she wholeheartedly attempts to will the Lie Detector into existence- someone who will be a witness to all her actions, someone who can attest that she is not a dream but extremely real. At least in stage acting, there is a decided break

between reality and make-believe, a moment for rest and relaxation when the actor returns to their real life after donning a different identity. For Sabina, there lies no such window for such a chance at repose. She has to perennially hide herself under the ephemeral cape of dream-making.

Interestingly enough, though, it is not only Sabina who come to be perceived through a curated lens. If one were to investigate a little bit further into her lovers, one would never be able to unearth their genuine personalities. It is because we always view the lovers only through Sabina's eyes. Nin writes in *The Novel of the Future*,

In *A Spy in the House of Love* I presented the male characters only at the moment they passed through the intense searchlight of Sabina's vision or desire of them. I intended to dramatize both the limitations and the intensity of passion, intensity rather than completeness in relationship. (94)

All the characters in the novella assume an element of abstraction. They are neither here nor there. Not just Sabina, but her lovers too become quite prone to vanishing into thin air at any moment. In such a frenzied act of hiding and seeking, the truth remains perennially hidden from the grasp of the readers. Rootless as it may seem, the truth of Sabina does erupt from cracks and fissures, quite open to be deciphered, if one knows where to look. Unfortunately, Sabina's lovers, and sometimes even Sabina herself, were crafted by Nin to be always lost in the labyrinthian excess of Sabina's desires.

Conclusion:

Anaïs Nin's novella, *A Spy in the House of Love*, assumes a critical ephemerality that is rarely seen in works of fiction. Sabina sparks in the reader a yearning for a frenzy of desire, a desire to inhabit this alternate dreamlike state that resists all attempts at definition and classification. The only definition it allows is of its ephemerality principle, shining through the cracks and

fissures detected in the persona of Sabina. Even then, one fails to fully define her. It is this refusal to be categorised and identified that differentiates Sabina from the rest. When she confesses, “I want to trespass boundaries, erase all identifications, anything which fixes one permanently into one mould, one place without hope of change” (Nin, 116), the reader feels it deeply inside their hearts. It reminds the reader of their own shackles to their own quotidian life and makes them yearn to reach out to the ephemeral, to inject into their bloodstreams the ebullient evanescence that runs through Sabina’s veins. The ephemerality that is central to this novella succeeds in upholding the intuitive ambiguity of female sexuality that Nin felt could not be captured by a male model of writing. Through the creation of a multiplicitous character like Sabina, who refuses to be pinned down, Nin was perhaps trying to emphasise how the multiplicity of female desire can only be encountered through its ephemeral traces. To return once more to Muñoz, the ephemeral in the novella assumes an epistemological clarity founded in the fleeting, where Sabina exists both as an innuendo and a fact, a fictive truth that can only be explored by giving up one’s desire to signify. This ephemerality principle, as detected in this novella, therefore, is not just a random choice of stylistics but rather Anaïs Nin’s conscious decision to embody a gendered epistemology rooted in the fragmented felt.

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